

A new Pb^{II} selective PVC membrane electrode based on tris(2-benzothiazolylmethyl)amine as an ionophore

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Abstract : A new poly(vinyl chloride) membrane electrode for selective potentiometric determination of Pb^{II} ions based on tris(2-benzothiazolylmethyl)amine(t) as an ionophore was prepared. The electrode exhibits a Nernstian response 30.0 ± 0.1 mV decade⁻¹ for lead ions over a wide concentration range of 1.0×10^{-7} to 1.0×10^{-2} M with a lower detection limit 5.2×10^{-8} . It has a fast response time 10 s and can be used for at least 4 months without any divergence in potential. The electrode can be used in the pH range 1.8–6.8. The electrode can also be used in partially non-aqueous media having up to 30% (v/v) methanol, ethanol or acetone content with no significant change in the value of slope or working concentration range. The proposed electrode shows fairly good discriminating ability towards lead ions in comparison with some alkali, alkaline earth, transition and heavy metal ions. It was successfully applied as an indicator electrode in potentiometric titration of lead ions with EDTA.

Keywords : PVC membrane electrode, lead ion, PVC membrane, tris(2-benzothiazolylmethyl)amine, potentiometry.

Introduction

The increasing use of ion electrodes (ISEs) in the fields of environmental, agricultural and medicinal analysis is stimulating analytical chemists to develop new electrodes for fast, accurate, reproducible and selective determination of various species. In the past few decades, considerable efforts have led to the development of selective sensors for alkali, alkaline earth and heavy metals¹.

Ion-selective electrodes (ISE) constructed on ion carriers are well established for many inorganic cations. During the past two decades, a large number of neutral cyclic and noncyclic compounds have been developed and have found widespread applications in potentiometric and optical sensors for the determination of respective ions in real samples².

The design and function of synthetic neutral ion carriers for cation selective membrane sensors are usually based on such diverse parameters as the structure and cavity

size of the ion carrier, the stability and selectivity of its metal ion complexes and the solubility and extraction ability of the target ion into the membrane phase.

The research on fabrication of new electrodes has caused a fundamental development in potentiometry over the past few decades³. Lead is ubiquitous in the environment and is hazardous⁴. As per Indian Standard Institution (ISI) specification, the tolerance limit for the discharge of lead into drinking water is 0.1 ppm⁵ and in land surface is 1.0 ppm⁶.

The recognized potential for human safety hazards presented by lead in the environment necessitates monitoring of its concentration in industrial effluents. The use of ion-selective electrodes for the detection of lead has received much interest and many ligands have been investigated as sensing agents in electrodes based on ionophore doped poly(vinyl chloride) (PVC) membranes^{2,7-18}.

In this work, we introduce a new selective and sensi-

tive Pb^{2+} PVC membrane electrode based on tris(2-benzothiazolylmethyl)amine as an ionophore (Fig. 1), for potentiometric determination of a wide concentration range of Pb^{2+} ion over alkali, alkaline earth and several transition metal ions.

Fig. 1. Structure of ionophore.

Experimental

Reagents and equipments :

Reagent grade plasticizers dibutylphthalate (DBP), dioctylphthalate (DOP), dioctyl sebacate (DOS), nitrobenzene (NB), dimethyl sebacate (DMS), *n*-butylacetate (NBA), anion additive sodium tetraphenylborate (NaTPB), tetrahydrofuran (THF), high molecular weight PVC, were purchased from Merck and used as received. Lead nitrate (from Merck) was used without any further purification, except for vacuum drying over P_4O_{10} , as a lead salt for the study of the membrane electrode. All the metal salt solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water and solutions of different concentrations were made by serial dilution of the 0.1 M stock solutions. The C, H and N

data were obtained by using a Carlo-Erba 1106 elemental analyzer. IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 137 instrument as KBr pellets. 1H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker DRX 500 spectrometer in $DMSO-d_6$.

Synthesis of tris(2-benzothiazolylmethyl)amine (NTBT) (ionophore) :

Nitrilotriacetic acid (19.1 g, 0.1 mol) and *o*-aminobenzenethiol (37.5.0 g, 0.3 mol) were mixed and heated slowly up to 190–200 °C. At around 100 °C an initial reaction occurs with frothing and rapid evolution of ammonia gas. The temperature of reaction mixture was maintained at 190–200 °C for 7 h for the evolution of ammonia gas was evolved. The product was cooled and the solid extracted into dichloromethane and refluxed with decolorizing charcoal. The solution was filtered and reduced in volume to give buff coloured crystals. Recrystallization was effected from dichloromethane and the product dried under vacuum over P_4O_{10} . The chemical characterization of the synthesized compound was carried out by the spectroscopic methods. The results obtained were similar to those reported earlier¹⁹. Anal. Calcd. for $C_{24}H_{18}N_4S_3$: C, 62.88; H, 3.93; N, 12.22; Found : C, 62.75; H, 3.80; N, 12.10; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) (ppm) : 4.37 (s) (28), 7.9 (m) (28), 7.4 (m) (28); IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 1626, 1596 (C=N).

Preparation of membrane electrode :

The general procedure was used to prepare the PVC membrane electrode as reported earlier²⁰. A number of membranes incorporating the active ingredient, anion additive and plasticizer in different compositions in PVC matrix were fabricated (Table 1). Varying amounts of the ionophore and an appropriate amount of PVC were dissolved in a minimum amount of THF. The anion additive

Table 1. Composition and performance characteristics of Pb^{II} -selective electrode (w/w)%

Sl. No.	PVC	Plasticizer	Ionophore	NaTPB	Slope (mV decade ⁻¹)	Working concentration range (M)
1.	36	–	3	3	21.2 ± 0.5	6.4 × 10 ⁻⁶ to 1.0 × 10 ⁻³
2.	33	59 (DBP)	2	6	25.0 ± 0.7	1.8 × 10 ⁻⁶ to 1.0 × 10 ⁻³
3.	30	61 (DOS)	4	5	26.5 ± 0.4	2.5 × 10 ⁻⁷ to 1.0 × 10 ⁻⁴
4.	31	61 (NB)	5	3	22.7 ± 0.2	4.2 × 10 ⁻⁶ to 1.0 × 10 ⁻²
5.	30	64 (DMS)	4	2	24.0 ± 0.3	1.5 × 10 ⁻⁵ to 1.0 × 10 ⁻²
6.	31	63 (DOP)	4	2	30.0 ± 0.2	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁷ to 1.0 × 10 ⁻²
7.	32	60 (DOP)	6	2	28.2 ± 0.5	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁷ to 1.0 × 10 ⁻²

(NaTPB) and plasticizers, DBP, DOP, DOS, NB and DMS were also added to get membranes of different compositions. The solutions thus obtained, after complete dissolution of various components, were poured into acrylic rings placed on a smooth glass plate and allowed to evaporate at room temperature. After 48 h, transparent membranes of 0.5 mm thickness were obtained which were then cut to size and attached to a Pyrex tube with the help of Araldite. It is known that the sensitivity, linearity and selectivity obtained for a given ionophore depends significantly on the membrane composition and nature of plasticizer used²¹. Thus, the ratio of membrane ingredients, time of contact, concentration of equilibrating solution, etc. were optimized after a good deal of experimentation to provide membranes, which generate reproducible and stable potentials. The membranes having only PVC as membrane ingredient (dummy membranes) have also been prepared to observe whether any background potentials being produced due to binding material or not. The potentials were not generated without the electroactive material in the membrane.

Potential measurements :

All the potential measurements were carried out at 25 ± 1 °C with a digital potentiometer (Model 5652 A, ECIL, India). Saturated calomel electrode (SCE) was used as a reference electrode. The electrochemical system is presented as follows :

Results and discussion

It is well known that the synthesized ionophore (tris(2-benzothiazolylmethyl)amine (NTBT) is able to form stable 1 : 1 (ligand : metal) complexes with a metal ions¹⁹. Due to its water insolubility as well as its tendency to form a selective and stable complex with Pb²⁺, the synthesized ionophore (Fig. 1) was employed in this work as a proper ligand for lead selective electrode.

Effect of membrane compositions :

A number of membrane compositions were investigated by varying the ratio of plasticizers and the ionophore and the results are given in Table 1 and Fig. 2. In neutral carrier membranes, plasticizers that are compatible with the ionophore provide a smooth surface to the membrane and hence enhance the response characteristics²². A membrane without plasticizer was first prepared and its effect was initially studied (electrode no. 1). The nature of the plasticizer influences the dielectric constant and the mobility of the ions in the membrane. These membrane solvents are seen to strongly influence the working concentration range and the slope of the electrode. It was observed that the electrode no. 5 with DOP as plasticizer was found to give the best response in terms

Fig. 2. Variations in cell potential of without and with plasticizers DOP, DBP, DOS, DMS and NB respectively, with Pb²⁺ concentration.

of the slope and the concentration range. The slopes in the case of the other plasticizers (DBP, DOP, DOS, NB and DMS) are sub-Nernstian (Table 1). The potentiometric response of the electrode towards Pb^{II} ions is found to be dependent on the concentration of the ionophore used. Different compositions (w/w%) of the ionophore were also tried to obtain the right composition of ionophore that gives the best response characteristics. The maximum sensitivity was observed for 4% (w/w) of the ionophore. On increasing the ionophore content, the slopes are affected; this may be related to the change in the water uptake capacity of the membrane.

The effect of the anionic additive was also studied. Anionic additives are beneficial as they contain ionic sites with a charge sign opposite to that of the primary ion and thus improve the Nernstian response of the electrode²³⁻²⁶. These lipophilic additives help in reducing the membrane resistance²⁷, improving the selectivity²⁸⁻³⁰ and reducing the interference from sample anions^{31,32}. There is a great improvement in the potentiometric response on the addition of the anionic additive, NaTPB (2 wt%).

Thus, the best composition was found to be 31 : 4 : 63 : 2 (PVC : I : DOP : NaTPB). And it gave a Nernstian slope of $30 \pm 1.0 \text{ mV decade}^{-1}$ of activity for the concentration range 1.0×10^{-7} to $1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$. The detection limit was calculated from the graph by the intersection of the two extrapolated linear segments of the calibration plot and was found to be $5.2 \times 10^{-8} \text{ M}$.

Effect of internal solution :

The proposed electrode was also examined at different concentrations of inner reference solution (1.0×10^{-1} to $1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$) and potential response of the electrode membrane has been observed. It was found that the best results in terms of slope and working concentration range has been obtained with internal solution of activity $1.0 \times 10^{-1} \text{ M}$. Thus, $1.0 \times 10^{-1} \text{ M}$ concentration of the reference solution was quite appropriate for the smooth functioning of the proposed electrode.

Effect of pH and non-aqueous effect :

The influence of pH of the test solution on the potential response of the lead electrode was tested at a $1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M Pb}^{2+}$ concentration over the pH range 1-7, adjusted by using NaOH or HNO_3 , and the results are shown in Fig. 3. As seen, the potential remained constant from pH 1.8-6.8. The observed potential increases below and above this pH range may be due to the simultaneous response of the electrode to Pb^{2+} and H^+ and Pb^{2+} and Li^+ , respectively³³.

The performance of the membrane electrode was also tested in partially non-aqueous media using methanol-water, ethanol-water and acetone-water mixtures. The electrode worked satisfactorily in the mixtures having up to 30% (v/v) (methanol, ethanol and acetone) nonaqueous content without showing any considerable change in working concentration range or slope (Table 2). However, above 30% non-aqueous content the potentials showed drift with time.

Fig. 3. Effect of pH on cell potential of electrode at $1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$.

Table 2. Effect of partially non-aqueous medium on the working of Pb²⁺ electrode

Non-aqueous content (% , v/v)	Slope (mV decade ⁻¹ of activity)	Working concentration range (M)
0	30	1.0×10^{-7} to 1.0×10^{-2}
Methanol :		
10	30	1.0×10^{-7} to 1.0×10^{-2}
20	29.8	1.3×10^{-7} to 1.0×10^{-2}
30	29.8	1.6×10^{-7} to 1.0×10^{-2}
Ethanol :		
10	30	1.0×10^{-7} to 1.0×10^{-2}
20	29.9	1.3×10^{-7} to 1.0×10^{-2}
30	29.8	1.6×10^{-7} to 1.0×10^{-2}
Acetone :		
10	30	1.0×10^{-7} to 1.0×10^{-2}
20	29.9	1.3×10^{-7} to 1.0×10^{-2}
30	29.9	1.6×10^{-7} to 1.0×10^{-2}

Dynamic response time behavior of the proposed electrode :

Dynamic response time is an important factor for lead(II) ion selective electrode. In this study, the practical response time has Fig. 4 been recorded (for the electrode no. 6) by changing solutions with different Pb²⁺ concentrations. The measurement sequence was from the lower (1.0×10^{-6} M) to the higher (1.0×10^{-2} M) concentra-

tion. The actual potential versus time traces is shown in Fig. 6. As it is seen, the electrode reached the equilibrium response in a very short time of about 10 s and the response of the electrode was remained constant up to 15 min.

To evaluate the reversibility of the electrode, a similar procedure in the opposite direction was adopted. The measurement has been performed in the sequence of high-to-low from (1.0×10^{-2} to 1.0×10^{-3} M) sample concentrations. The results showed that, the potentiometric response of the electrode was reversible; although the time needed to reach equilibrium values (35 s) were longer than that of low-to-high sample concentrations.

Life time of proposed electrode :

The lifetime of the electrode having DOP plasticizer was determined by recording its potentials at an optimum pH value and by plotting its calibration curves for each day. It was observed that there was no significant change in the slope and working range of the electrode for a period of 4 months. After 4 months a slight gradual decreases in the slopes (from 30 ± 0.2 to 27 ± 0.5 mV decade⁻¹) was observed. During this period, the electrodes were used over extended period of time (one hour per day). However, it is important to emphasize that the membranes were stored in a 1.0×10^{-2} M Pb(NO₃)₂ solution when not in use.

Fig. 4. Dynamic response time of the membrane electrode.

Potentiometric selectivity coefficient :

The selectivity behavior is the most important characteristic of an ion selective electrode as it determines the applicability of any electrode in the presence of foreign ions in the samples. Selectivity interprets relative electrode response for the primary cation over other cations present in solution, which is usually expressed in terms of potentiometric selectivity coefficient. The selectivity coefficient values were calculated by fixed interference method (FIM) as suggested by sa'ez de Viteri and Diamond³⁴. In the fixed interference method (FIM), the potential of the cell is measured for a number of solutions containing interfering ion of constant activity a^Y but varying values of activity of primary ion a^X . The value of selectivity coefficient is then calculated using the following equation,

$$K_{\text{pot.}}^{XY} = a^X / (a^Y)^{Z_X/Z_Y}$$

where a^X is the activity of primary ion and a^Y is the activity of interfering ion Y . Z_X and Z_Y are the charge on primary and interfering ions. In this, the potential was measured for solutions containing varying concentration of Pb^{2+} and fixed interfering ion concentration ($1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$). The selectivity coefficients so calculated by this method are summarized in Table 3. As it is seen, the electrode exhibits selective response toward Pb^{2+} . A value of selectivity coefficient equal to 1.0 would indicate that the membrane responds equally to primary as well as interfering ion. A value smaller than 1.0 indicates that it responds more to primary ion than interfering ion and in such a case, the electrode is said to be selective to pri-

Table 3. Selectivity coefficients of electrode no. 6c as determined by FIM

Interfering ion (B)	Selectivity coefficient ($K_{\text{pot.}}^{A,B}$)
NH_4^+	1.6×10^{-4}
Li^+	1.8×10^{-4}
Zn^{2+}	2.5×10^{-3}
Mn^{2+}	2.8×10^{-3}
Co^{2+}	3.7×10^{-3}
Ba^{2+}	4.2×10^{-2}
Cd^{2+}	3.3×10^{-3}
Fe^{3+}	3.9×10^{-3}
Mg^{2+}	2.7×10^{-3}
Ce^{3+}	3.2×10^{-3}
Cr^{3+}	4.6×10^{-4}

mary ion over interfering ion. It is seen from the table that selectivity coefficients are in the order of 10^{-4} or lower for almost all diverse ions tested. Thus, these ions would not cause any significant interference in the estimation of Pb^{2+} ions by this electrode unless present in large amounts. The electroactive material of the membrane is ionophore and thus allows the transport of ions only, hence the membrane responds to ions only. The membrane would not allow organic substances to transport; hence they should not cause any interference.

Analytical application :

Potentiometric titration was performed by using the proposed electrode as an indicator electrode in the determination of lead ions. A 20 mL solution of $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ was titrated against $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ EDTA and change in potential was plotted in Fig. 5. The titration plot obtained at pH 4.0, which indicates that the electrode is highly selective to Pb^{2+} ions. The inflexion points of the plot correspond to the 1 : 1 stoichiometry of lead-EDTA complex. Thus, it is clear that the concentration of lead ion in solution can be accurately determined from the resulting neat titration curve providing a sharp end point.

Fig. 5. Potentiometric titration curve of a $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ Pb^{2+} solution (20 mL) with $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ EDTA.

Conclusion

The plasticized PVC-based membrane electrode incorporating tris(2-benzothiazolylmethyl)amine as an ionophore, DOP as solvent mediator and NaTPB as anion additive in a PVC matrix ratio of 31 : 4 : 63 : 2 (PVC : I : DOP : NaTPB) could be used to determine Pb^{2+} in the

concentration range 1.0×10^{-7} to 1.0×10^{-2} M with a slope of 30.0 mV decade⁻¹ of activity. The electrode works in a wide pH range (1.8–6.8) with a response time of 10 s. The selectivity of the electrode towards Pb²⁺ over other cations is quite good and the lifetime of the assembly is 4 months. In addition, the membrane electrode can be used as an indicator electrode in potentiometric titration involving Pb²⁺ ions against EDTA.

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References

1. S. P. Parker, "Concise Encyclopedia of Science and Technology", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1984.
2. P. Bühlmann, E. Pretsch and E. Backer, *Chem. Rev.*, 1998, **98**, 1593.
3. Y. Umezawa, "CRC Handbook of Ion-selective Electrodes", CRC Press, Boca Raton, FL, 1990, 460.
4. C. Namasivayam and K. Ranganathan, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.*, 1995, **34**, 869.
5. ISI Drinking Water Specification, 1991, IS : 10500.
6. ISI Tolerance Limits for Industrial Effluents Prescribed by Indian Standard Institution, IS : 2490, Part II, Bureau of Indian Standards, Manak Bhawan, 9, Bahadur Shah Zafar Marg, New Delhi, India, 1982.
7. E. Lindner, K. Toth and E. Pungor, *Anal. Chem.*, 1984, **56**, 1127.
8. S. Kamata and K. Onoyama, *Anal. Chem.*, 1991, **63**, 1295.
9. S. R. Shen and J. Shih, *Analyst*, 1992, **117**, 1691.
10. S. K. Srivastava, V. K. Gupta and S. Jain, *Analyst*, 1995, **120**, 495.
11. N. Tavakkoli and M. Shamsipur, *Anal. Lett.*, 1996, **29**, 2269.
12. N. Tavakkoli, Z. Khojasteh, H. Sharghi and M. Shamsipur, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1998, **360**, 203.
13. A. Abbaspour and F. Tavakol, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1999, **378**, 145.
14. M. F. Mousavi, M. B. Barzegar and S. Sahari, *Sensors and Actuators (B)*, 2001, **73**, 199.
15. V. K. Gupta, R. Mangla and S. Agarwal, *Electroanalysis*, 2002, **14**, 15.
16. V. K. Gupta, A. K. Jain and P. Kumar, *Sensors and Actuators (B)*, 2006, **120**, 259.
17. S. Y. Kazemia, M. Shamsipur and H. Sharghi, *J. Haz. Mat.*, 2009, **172**, 68.
18. H. A. Arida, A. S. Al-haddad and M. J. Schöning, *Int. J. Electrochem. Sci.*, 2011, **6**, 3858.
19. L. K. Thompson, R. G. Ball and J. Trotter, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1980, **58**, 1566.
20. P. K. Tomar, S. Chandra, A. Malik, A. Kumar and A. Kumar, *Anal. Bioanal. Electrochem.*, 2011, **3**, 119.
21. T. Katsu, K. Ido, K. Takaishi and H. Yokosu, *Sensors Actuators (B)*, 2002, **87**, 331.
22. K. Cammann, "Working with Ion-selective Electrodes", Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 1979, 82.
23. W. E. Morf, D. Amman and W. Simon, *Chimia*, 1974, **28**, 65.
24. P. Bühlmann, S. Yajima, K. Tohda and Y. Umezawa, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1995, **40**, 3021.
25. P. Bühlmann, S. Yajima, K. Tohda, K. Umezawa, S. Nishizawa and Y. Umezawa, *Electroanalysis*, 1995, **7**, 811.
26. S. Yajima, K. Tohda, P. Bühlmann and Y. Umezawa, *Anal. Chem.*, 1997, **69**, 1919.
27. D. Amman, "Ion-selective Microelectrodes : Principles, Design and Application", Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 1986, 15.
28. D. Amman, W. E. Morf, P. Anker, P. C. Meier, E. Pretsch and W. Simon, *Ion-Sel. Electrode Rev.*, 1983, **5**, 3.
29. P. C. Meier, W. E. Morf, M. Laubli and W. Simon, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1984, **156**, 1.
30. R. Eugster, P. M. Gehrig, W. E. Morf, U. E. Spichiger and W. Simon, *Anal. Chem.*, 1991, **63**, 2285.
31. W. E. Morf, G. Kahr and W. Simon, *Anal. Lett.*, 1974, **7**, 9.
32. M. Huser, P. M. Gehrig, W. E. Morf, W. Simon, C. Lindner, J. Jeney, K. Toth and E. Pungor, *Anal. Chem.*, 1991, **63**, 1380.
33. M. Shamsipur, S. Rouhani, M. R. Ganjali, H. Eshghi and H. Sharghi, *Microchem. J.*, 1999, **63**, 202.
34. F. J. Sa'ez de Viteri and D. Diamond, *Analyst*, 1994, **119**, 749.

